

Project Title **Implementing FAIR Workflows: a proof of concept study in the field of consciousness**

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D3.1 Track Connections with the Project Dashboard

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Executive summary

The 'Implementing FAIR Workflows' project aims to develop a FAIR workflow that can be applied to Cognitive Neuroscience research. It focuses on leveraging persistent identifiers (PIDs) and metadata to identify and connect various research outputs, thereby enhancing their accessibility and reusability. Central to the project is a dashboard designed to display various research outputs related to a research project, crediting researchers and institutes and highlighting interconnections. The dashboard utilizes DataCite Commons, a web interface for exploring the PID Graph - a network of scholarly objects, people, and organizations connected through PIDs and metadata.

User workshops were conducted to gather insights and challenges in Neuroscience research, particularly regarding non-traditional research outputs like datasets and code. These insights guided the design of the dashboard, which focuses on showcasing a broad range of outputs and addressing the need for changes in research culture and recognition metrics. The dashboard's features include a Related Works list, downloadable reports, data visualizations, and a project facet for easier discovery. These features aim to consolidate (meta)data and usage information, simplifying reporting processes and enhancing visibility and acknowledgment for researchers.

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Introduction

The 'Implementing FAIR Workflows' project aims to develop and put into practice an exemplary FAIR workflow in real research environments. It brings together research infrastructure experts and researchers to improve the management and presentation of research outputs in Cognitive Neuroscience. Aligned with the FAIR principles, the project focuses on making research outputs more accessible and reusable through open sharing and the use of persistent identifiers (PIDs).

At the heart of this project is the creation of a project dashboard, an interface that dynamically displays related entities throughout the project lifecycle. The dashboard leverages the PID Graph¹ developed under project FREYA², a network of PIDs connected in standardized ways, to expose uniquely identified researchers, organizations, grants, and outputs. Once captured in the PID Graph, the entities are then mapped to the machine readable GraphQL API, which is used to surface information to the web interface. This dashboard allows researchers to evaluate a research study in its entirety and obtain information that is often not readily available to them, such as which investigators contributed to a dataset or software; and how much a dataset was viewed, downloaded, cited and reused. The dashboard also organizes the relevant data points into insights and presents them in digestible formats such as tabs, lists, and data visualizations. The goal of the dashboard is to introduce nuance into the research process and incentivize different stakeholder groups to invest in adopting open and FAIR practices.

The metadata behind the PIDs, generated by researchers and data managers practicing FAIR sharing, supported by data repositories and research tools that integrate with PID functionalities, are the key to make the PID Graph meaningful, and the dashboard useful. Complete, accurate, and timely metadata enable users to track connections between research projects and outputs, as well as the people, organizations, and grants involved. Additionally, it provides easy access to usage statistics, i.e., citation, view, and download statistics, of project-related works.

This report offers a brief introduction to the DataCite Commons platform, outlines the steps taken towards developing the dashboard, and the features implemented on the dashboard. The 'User Story' section documents the user workshops organized to gather user stories to guide product design and technical specifications of the dashboard. The 'Product Specification' section delves into the details of design decisions and implementation requirements.

The Implementing FAIR Workflows project dashboard can be accessed at <https://commons.datacite.org/doi.org/10.60581/zaev-6p15>

¹ Fenner, M., & Aryani, A. (2019). *Introducing the PID Graph*. <https://doi.org/10.5438/JWVF-8A66>

² <https://doi.org/10.3030/777523>

DataCite Commons

DataCite Commons' is a web interface overlay designed for exploring the PID Graph³. The PID Graph is a comprehensive network of various types of scholarly objects, such as publications, datasets, research software, and other research outputs, uniquely identified and connected through the assignment of PIDs and metadata⁴.

DataCite Commons was developed through the collaborative efforts of the FREYA project and marked a significant advancement in scholarly communication upon its official launch. The development process of Commons adopted a user-centric methodology, beginning with the gathering and prioritizing of user stories from a broad range of communities. These stories encapsulate challenges and needs based on real-world use cases, including the aggregation of scholarly outputs, the versioning of data and software, and the grouping of all outputs related to a specific publication. The GraphQL language was chosen for the underlying technical architecture of the PID Graph, due to its efficacy in managing complex queries and offering a more robust and efficient query handling process.

In line with these user-centric principles, the development of the project dashboard developed as part of the FAIR Workflows project inherited the workflow from the original Commons. This approach involved engaging core user groups through workshops to discuss their challenges and needs, as detailed in the 'User Workshops' section.

³ Fenner, M. (2020). *DataCite Commons at your service*. <https://doi.org/10.5438/MKPQ-4W71>

⁴ Fenner, M. (2020a). *DataCite Commons - Exploiting the Power of PIDs and the PID Graph*. <https://doi.org/10.5438/F4DF-4817>

User Workshops

We conducted a series of workshops with a focus group consisting of project team and advisory committee members. Initially, the goal was to identify a set of insights and challenges, which we then transformed into user stories. In the second stage, we presented these user stories back to the focus group for validation and conducted a prioritization exercise to support feature design and development scheduling. This report focuses on the two main workshops that yielded the primary set of insights used in the design and development process.

Gathering insights and challenges

The first workshop was organized to introduce DataCite Commons and the concept of the project dashboard to domain experts. Participants were selected from the project advisory group and represented the perspectives of senior researchers, funders, and research tool providers in the field of neuroscience.

The goal of the workshop was to identify activities and challenges that neuroscience researchers face, particularly when trying to demonstrate the impact of non-traditional research outputs such as datasets, code, etc.

Figure 1. Insights collected from the workshop participants.

During live interviews, participants commented on specific scenarios related to sharing and demonstrating research outputs throughout the project lifecycle. These insights were documented in short notes and subsequently summarized into the following themes (see all notes in the appendix):

Diverse types of outputs are needed to paint the whole picture. The participants emphasized the production and sharing of a wide range of research outputs, beyond traditional papers. This includes Jupyter notebooks, pre-registrations, datasets, etc., and the need to establish

standardized ways to evaluate the quality of shared outputs. This is important for both reusability and fair recognition/crediting.

Output sharing requires changes to the current research culture. The participants also pointed out that the underlying obstacle to wider adoption of FAIR and open sharing practices is, on the one hand, a lack of awareness and incentives, and on the other, the still-predominant notion of the value of traditional metrics. This leads to a lack of community endorsed resources as well as clear, practical routes to implementation.

Being able to easily aggregate outputs across different venues supports efficient reporting to funders and communication among peers. The participants noted that the primary purpose of various reports, such as project reports for the funding agency and annual reports for the employing institute, is to publicly demonstrate the productivity and impact of research through metrics like the number of journal publications, openly shared datasets, and citations from sources such as Google Scholar. They also noted the importance of these reports in providing updates to collaborators and stakeholders about research progress, and emphasized the role of open communication through conferences, journals, blogs, and social media throughout the project period in enhancing recognition and compliance.

Research infrastructure and tools play a significant role in supporting and simplifying workflows. The participants highlighted the use of tools like Jupyter notebooks for reporting analyses and the increasing demand from funders for the open accessibility of outputs, acknowledging the challenges in providing infrastructure and tools, and improving their usability to gain community recognition. This discussion led to the notion that such tools and platforms are pivotal in transforming research practices and facilitating reuse.

Based on the insights gathered from the workshop, it was clear that the project dashboard design must encapsulate the full spectrum of scholarly contributions. It should reflect the diverse types of outputs that are often excluded from traditional metrics, acknowledging the nuanced and multifaceted nature of research work, reporting, dissemination, and evaluation.

The central role of research infrastructure and tools in supporting and simplifying the intricate workflows of researchers is evident. The project dashboard needs to incorporate features that facilitate easy reporting, ensure compliance, and enhance discoverability.

The participants also highlighted a few risks that we should be aware of, and take measures to mitigate when designing the user interface:

1. The uneven adoption of open and FAIR sharing practices among the researchers will limit the usability of the project dashboard - outputs that are shared without PIDs or without metadata connections will not show up on the dashboard.

2. The data sources and scope of inclusion need to be made explicit for users to confidently interpret the data on the dashboard; however, relying on narrow technical definitions risks making the interface difficult to use.
3. Relying on PID metadata for project information enables the dashboard to reflect updates across platforms, at the same time the dashboard will also reflect evolving implementation rules on various platforms, leading to changes or breakage of links reflected on the dashboard.

User story validation and prioritization

A second workshop was arranged with the aim to iterate on the user stories developed based on the input from the first workshop. The design team synthesized the data and formulated the user stories based on a revised “As a [role], I [want to], [so that].” template.

The user stories were first shared with the workshop participants for validation via a collaborative document. The group was invited to comment on and make suggestions to the draft user stories to ensure that they fully reflect their perspectives and comments provided during the previous workshop.

The workshop was held to present the finalized stories to the core user representatives and conduct a prioritization exercise to define the design and development priorities. The factors considered for prioritization included input from the advisory group (who voted on the relative importance of each user story), how well each user story aligned with overall project goals, and technical feasibility. The results from the workshops provided sufficient data for the design and development team to generate a product specification.

User Stories

When I need to demonstrate impact, I want to be able to collect a list of all the scholarly outputs associated with my project, so I can not only show direct project outputs, but also scholarly works that have cited, referenced, or are related to my work in any other capacity.

When I need to report to my institution or funders, I want to be able to generate a list of all the scholarly outputs associated with my project created in a defined range of years, so that I can provide a comprehensive overview of my work, with context, for project evaluation.

When I have to report to my institution or funders, I want to aggregate the number of scholarly outputs associated with my project, so I can demonstrate quantitatively the volume of outputs from the project to aid better evaluation.

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When I have to report to my institution or funders, I want to aggregate the usage statistics of the project outputs, so I can demonstrate quantitatively the impact of the project outputs for better evaluation.

When I have to demonstrate the overall outputs resulting from the project, I want to be able to show the key contributors in the project team and what outputs they contributed to, so that the researchers are fairly credited.

When I have to report to my institution or funders, I want to be able to export the linked scholarly outputs in a format suitable (citation styles) for my reporting. So I can reduce the time of report preparation.

When using the dashboard, I want to be able to identify the sources (either, people, organizations, platforms) of the displayed data, so I can make informed decisions about research tool adoption.

Table 1. Prioritized list of user stories.

Product specification

This section details the final specification of the project dashboard on DataCite Commons. Together, the five features outlined below form the project dashboard page, based on PIDs and the associated metadata registered for the corpus of entities related to a research project.

Terminology

Relationships, relation types, and their directions are difficult to get clarity on without common terminology. Here are some definitions used in the specification document:

Main Work DOI	The DOI that a given Work page is about; i.e., in https://commons.datacite.org/doi.org/{id} , the {id} is the Main Work DOI.
Related DOI	A DOI that is related to the Main Work DOI.
Related Works	The list of Related DOIs.
Outgoing link	A connection derived from a RelatedIdentifier in the Main Work DOI's metadata, pointing to a Related DOI.
Incoming link	A connection derived from a RelatedIdentifier on the Related DOI's metadata, pointing to the Main Work DOI.

Table 2. Terms and definitions used in the specification.

Scope and dashboard feature overview

For the purpose of developing the proof-of-concept dashboard in this project, the identifier chosen to represent the 'Project' resource type are DataCite DOIs that meet the following criteria:

- `(resourceType == "Project") AND (resourceTypeGeneral == "Other" OR resourceTypeGeneral == "Text")`

The screenshot shows a DataCite Commons project record page. At the top left is the DataCite Commons logo. A search bar is at the top center. Navigation tabs for 'Works', 'People', 'Organizations', and 'Repositories' are below the search bar. The main title is 'Implementing FAIR Workflows: A Proof of Concept Study in the Field of Consciousness' with a DOI link. Below the title are buttons for 'Add to ORCID Record' and 'Download Metadata'. The 'Description' tab is active, showing a detailed paragraph about the project's goals and methods. Below the description are buttons for 'Other', 'Psychology', and 'English'. On the left side, there is a 'Cite as' section with an APA citation format and a 'Share' section with icons for Email, Twitter, and Facebook.

Figure 2. Commons page of a project record before the development of the project dashboard.

The project dashboard page is a new subtype of the DataCite Commons Work pages, which display general information about a resource. The core metadata of the resource reflected on this page include the resource title, description, creators and contributors, funders, DOI registration information, language, subject keywords, and the repository that holds the DOI record. The Work page also displays the citation string in various formats and provides the option to download the metadata record. These elements are all retained for the project dashboard view.

For regular works, which are commonly research outputs, the work page displays a list of other works that are either cited by or cite the work on record. However, because the relationships between a project and its outputs are rarely denoted as citations, the project dashboard displays all associated works, including those which are not citations (Feature 1). These associated works can also be exported in a report format (Feature 2). To present the project and all its related entities in a digestible format—including different types of resources, people, and organizations—the dashboard also summarizes the volume of each entity type and their connections in a network graph (Feature 3). This graph provides evidence for evaluating the volume of work involved and the overall impact generated by the project. The project dashboard includes a visualization that summarizes the most productive contributors to the project and the types of outputs they contributed to, based on the metadata in the related work DOIs (Feature 4). This chart highlights

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top performers in a project beyond just the author list of the final journal article, increases the visibility of productive members of research projects, and promotes fair crediting. The final feature defined in the work package introduces “Project” to the Work Type facet, allowing users to filter results to find all projects related to their search term (Feature 5). While this facet is not directly presented on the project dashboard, it makes projects as a resource type more discoverable in Commons: the project facet feature is implemented on the search results page under the work search tab.

The screenshot shows the DataCite Commons interface for a project record. The title is "Implementing FAIR Workflows: A Proof of Concept Study in the Field of Consciousness" with a DOI of <https://doi.org/10.60581/zaev-6p15>. It has 1 citation and is licensed under CC BY. The page features a "Contributors" tab with a table listing individuals and their roles. On the left sidebar, there are buttons for "Add to ORCID Record" and "Download Metadata", and a "Download Reports" section with a dropdown menu set to "APA".

Description	Creators	Contributors	Funders	Registration
	Xiaoli Chen	DataCite		Project Leader
	Zefan Zheng	Max Planck Institute for Empirical Aesthetics		Researcher
	Tanya Brown	Max Planck Institute for Empirical Aesthetics		Project Manager
	Australian Research Data Commons			Work Package Leader
	California Digital Library			Work Package Leader
	Stanford University			Work Package Leader
	ChronosHub			Work Package Leader
	Dryad Digital Repository			Work Package Leader

Figure 3. Commons page of a project record after the implementation of new features, showing Feature 2 (Downloadable reports).

Figure 4. Commons page of a project record after the implementation of new features, showing Feature 1 (Related Works list) and Feature 4 (Related Works people/output types visualization).

Feature 1: Related Works list

User story: When I need to demonstrate impact, I want to be able to collect a list of all the scholarly outputs associated with my project, so I can not only show direct project outputs, but also scholarly works that have cited, referenced, or are related to my work in any other capacity.

Feature 1A: Display unified list of all Related Works

The Related Works list contains all works that are associated with the project DOI in the metadata, sorted into the following bins (shown as facets on the left column):

- Citations
- References
- Parts
- Is Part Of

- Other (new subcategory of other RelatedIdentifier-based relations).

These appear as one unified list that can be filtered and visualized as one group.

Figure 5. Facets (on the left column, isPartOf connection type not shown in this particular example) and visualized summary of the related works (right column) placed on top of the related works list (truncated).

Citations include:

- **Outgoing links:** Related DOIs connected via the Main Work DOI's metadata. The Main Work DOI has RelatedIdentifiers for these DOIs with any of the following relationTypes:
 - IsCitedBy
 - IsReferencedBy
 - IsSupplementTo
- **Incoming links:** Related DOIs connected via the Related DOIs' metadata. The Related DOIs have RelatedIdentifiers for the Main Work DOI with any of the following relationTypes:
 - Cites
 - References
 - IsSupplementedBy

References include:

- **Outgoing links:** Related DOIs connected via the Main Work DOI's metadata. The Main Work DOI has RelatedIdentifiers for these DOIs with any of the following relationTypes:
 - Cites

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- References
- IsSupplementedBy
- Incoming links: Related DOIs connected via the Related DOIs' metadata. The Related DOIs have RelatedIdentifiers for the Main Work DOI with any of the following relationTypes:
 - IsCitedBy
 - IsReferencedBy
 - IsSupplementTo

Parts is defined using the "parts" aggregation, which includes cases where:

- the Main Work DOI HasPart Related DOI; or
- Related DOI IsPartOf Main Work DOI.

Is Part Of is defined using the "part of" aggregation, which includes cases where:

- the Main Work DOI IsPartOf Related DOI; or
- Related DOI HasPart Main Work DOI.

Other includes all other outgoing and incoming links not covered by the above categories:

- Outgoing links: Related DOIs connected via the Main Work DOI's metadata. The Main Work DOI has RelatedIdentifiers for these DOIs with any of the following relationTypes:
 - Explicit list of all current v4.4 relationTypes except IsCitedBy, Cites, IsReferencedBy, References, IsSupplementTo, and IsSupplementedBy, IsPartOf, HasPart.
- Incoming links: Related DOIs connected via the Related DOIs' metadata. The Related DOIs have RelatedIdentifiers for the Main Work DOI with any of the following relationTypes:
 - Explicit list of all current v4.4 relationTypes except IsCitedBy, Cites, IsReferencedBy, References, IsSupplementTo, and IsSupplementedBy, IsPartOf, HasPart.

The list of all current relationTypes except IsCitedBy, Cites, IsReferencedBy, References, IsSupplementTo, and IsSupplementedBy, IsPartOf, HasPart is:

- | | | |
|--------------------|-----------------------|--------------------|
| ● IsCitedBy | ● IsNewVersionOf | ● IsVariantFormOf |
| ● Cites | ● IsPreviousVersionOf | ● IsOriginalFormOf |
| ● IsSupplementTo | ● IsPartOf | ● IsIdenticalTo |
| ● IsSupplementedBy | ● HasPart | ● IsReviewedBy |
| ● IsContinuedBy | ● IsPublishedIn | ● Reviews |
| ● Continues | ● IsReferencedBy | ● IsDerivedFrom |
| ● Describes | ● References | ● IsSourceOf |
| ● IsDescribedBy | ● IsDocumentedBy | ● IsRequiredBy |
| ● HasMetadata | ● Documents | ● Requires |

- IsMetadataFor
- HasVersion
- IsVersionOf
- IsCompiledBy
- Compiles
- Obsoletes
- IsObsoletedBy

The source of this list is the DataCite Metadata Schema version 4.4⁵.

Feature 1B: Facet for “Connection Type”

When the Related Works list is included on a Work page, a facet for “Connection Type” is displayed with three options, with the scope of each as described in Feature 1A:

- Citations
- References
- Parts
- Is Part Of
- Other

Figure 6. Connection types facet.

Note that because the Main Work DOI may be related to any Related Work DOI in more than one way, a given Related Work DOI may appear in multiple categories. For example: a project “requires” a data management plan, and the data management plan “references” the project.

⁵

<https://github.com/datacite/schema/blob/master/source/meta/kernel-4.4/include/datacite-relationType-v4.xsd>

Currently, the facet implementation does not allow check-box selection of multiple facets to display all related works linked to the project DOI (main work DOI).

Feature 2: Downloadable reports

User story: When I need to report to my institution and/or funders, I want to be able to generate a list of all the scholarly outputs associated with my project created in a defined range of years, so that I can provide a comprehensive overview of my work, with context, for project evaluation.

This feature adds a link to the dashboard, allowing users to download a .csv file containing a list of all Related Works with one click. The list includes descriptions and formatted citations in APA style for up to 200 DOIs associated with the project.

- Related Works (CSV)

Figure 7. Downloadable reports link with tooltip

Specifically, the csv file contains the following columns:

- Title
- Publication Year
- DOI
- Description
- Formatted Citation
- Resource Type (General)
- Resource Type
- Connection Type
 - One or more of: Citation, Reference, Part, Is Part Of, Other Relation

The Resource Type (General) and Resource Type columns are included to help researchers highlight the diversity of project outputs with ease, when reporting to funders and institutes.

Feature 3: Connections visualization: force-directed graph

User Story: When I have to report to my institution or funders, I want to aggregate the number of scholarly outputs associated with my project, so I can demonstrate quantitatively the volume of outputs from the project to aid better evaluation.

Note: At the time of writing, this feature has been completed but is pending deployment and release.

Based on the user story, the research team additionally required the aggregated data of project related outputs to be presented as a graph, in order to demonstrate key output types, connections, and their frequencies in context, and in an easily digestible format. This feature implementation generates a force-directed graph⁶ that shows a high level overview of the different types of shared works connected to a Project and the connections between them. This visualization is based on the DOIs in the Related Works list and displays the connections between them. These Related DOIs are directly connected to the Project DOI (whether through an incoming or outgoing link).

Note that while the Related DOIs may be connected to other DOIs which are not in the Related Works list, these connections are out of scope for this visualization.

Figure 8. Example force-directed chart showing aggregated number related works by work-type and the number of links among them.

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Force-directed_graph_drawing

- Nodes: the graph includes a set of nodes representing the most frequent (top 10) work types (based on resourceTypeGeneral) among the related works. The number in the node represents the number of works of that type among all related works.
- Edges: the graph includes the number of connections between different types of works. The number on the edge represents the total number of unique connections established between two types of resources (without considering connection types). A Work is connected to a related Work through relatedIdentifiers.

The StudyRegistration⁷ work type was included in the recently released schema version 4.5 and the proposal for adding the Project work type is being reviewed. Currently both these types are filed under Text, reflected in the dominating Text node in the graph.

Feature 4: Related Works people/output types visualization: Sankey chart

User Story: When I have to demonstrate the overall outputs resulting from the project, I want to be able to show the key contributors in the project team and what outputs they contributed to, so that the researchers are fairly credited.

This feature showcases the top contributors to the project and how they contributed to the main types of output of the project. The Sankey chart⁸ shows two columns: person on the left, work-type on the right. It visualizes the number of times each person is associated with each work type.

⁷

<https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.5/appendices/appendix-1/resourceTypeGeneral/#studyregistration>

⁸ <https://www.data-to-viz.com/graph/sankey.html>

Figure 9. Example Sankey chart with 4 contributors on the left and 2 resource types on the right.

To surface the top contributors and work types, the dashboard processes the full list of works related to the project and generates a ranked list of people with ORCID iDs. This ranking is based on the number of works to which they are linked. For each person in this list, the dashboard counts how many works of each work type (resourceTypeGeneral) they are associated with.

Similarly, the dashboard then creates a ranked list of all work types based on all the work types retrieved in the previous step, summing across all of the top contributors. From this, the top work types are selected for visualization as a Sankey chart.

Feature 5: Project facet

This feature is implemented on the search result page under the Works tab. To make projects as a unique type of research object more discoverable, and the project dashboard a more prominent feature, we added a “Project” category in the Work Type facet selection on the left column of the DataCite Commons search result page.

Work Type	
<input type="checkbox"/> Text	167,955
<input type="checkbox"/> Project	72,435
<input type="checkbox"/> Dataset	362
<input type="checkbox"/> Journal Article	253
<input type="checkbox"/> Other	138
<input type="checkbox"/> Collection	60
<input type="checkbox"/> Preprint	42
<input type="checkbox"/> Dissertation	32
<input type="checkbox"/> Data Paper	30
<input type="checkbox"/> Software	29

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Figure 10. Example Work Type facet with “Project” resource type displayed⁹.

The facet filters search results to display only projects. Projects are identified with DataCite DOIs that meet the following criteria: (resourceType == “Project”) AND (resourceTypeGeneral == “Other” OR resourceTypeGeneral == “Text”).

Note that the work type facets section only shows the 10 most frequent work types based on the search result. The implementation of this feature acknowledges the importance of the “project” work-type, and hopefully will incentivize wider adoption of open research practices and increase the number of project DOIs being registered.

⁹ <https://commons.datacite.org/doi.org?query=client.uid:cos.osf>

Conclusion and future work

The project level dashboard is valuable for different stakeholders and different use cases. Aggregating project information based on the metadata of PIDs is a viable step forward to meet the needs of researchers, funders, and institutes to perform efficient reporting, comprehensive impact measurement, and reliable evaluation. We would like to thank our project advisory group for their contribution through the workshops and providing insightful feedbacks during the dashboard design and development process.

The data behind the dashboard is complex and presenting data in useful views is resource intensive - both in terms of computational resources and designing and developing the proof of concept. The dashboard features are designed to be closely integrated within the DataCite Commons platform, aiming to be improved upon and maintained long-term beyond the project period, as we continue to advocate for FAIR project workflows and promote the use cases of the project dashboard.

The power of the dashboard is as great as the quality of the data it is drawing from. The dashboard delivered in the project is a proof of concept, it still relies on the workflows to be implemented consistently across stakeholders - researchers to share outputs through repositories, research tools to integrate PID functionalities, research institutes and funding organizations to formally and effectively recognize open research practices and the value of FAIRly shared research outputs.

Currently, the dashboard is displayed for all DOIs that are registered with the relevant resource type. Going forward, we will work on a closer integration with RAiD, the Research Activity Identifier. It is our hope that the project dashboard will play a role in building the momentum toward the virtuous cycle of open science by surfacing the value of open and FAIR research practices at the project level.

Appendix

Full list of input from the user insights workshop.

- To produce other media for communicating research outputs. This includes Jupyter notebooks.
- To report research outputs that are not normally captured by other services. This includes pre-registrations and other kinds of outputs.
- Publish Conferences Publish Data (Sometimes) Reports to Funders
- To share code - in a way that can be tested and evaluated. This needs standardization.
- To highlight the value of outputs that normally don't contribute to the impact factor. This is to accurately recognize the value of all research outputs.
- enable people to access all the outputs as easily as they do a paper
- reporting protocols
- code sharing is less "valued"
- ways to promote OS via funders: policies, compliance, infrastructure to enable sharing/tracking/documenting
- data sharing and code sharing are sometimes taken into consideration
- code sharing is not necessarily embedded in a formal way into the publication, dataset, etc
- tracking of all the outputs is currently low-fi
- cultural changes need to be a focus; how do we change culture?
- bias to high impact factor publications - aim for different values
- data sharing rewarded by funding
- mechanisms are in place to share data, code, etc. we need to change culture!
- Impact Factor still the main "impact" measure
- Reports Grants to Agency Institutional Reports
- To report publicly how productive research has been - numbers of papers, datasets etc.
- To get updates from collaborators on what scientific products they produced. This information is needed to compile the reports for stakeholders.
- recognition by the community (with metrics)
- Produce reports for funders and other stakeholders to demonstrate research progress.
- impact: publishing, conferences, publishing dataset
- reports for grant agencies for institution
- to report impact publication are listed and citation counts are drawn from google scholar
- frequency of reporting varies (monthly, annually , etc)
- Media Conferences Journals Blogs, Social media
- recommendation - compliance - infrastructure - recognition - html -> latest version of pre-registration and link to the object query a paper for data the pb: how to recognize this?
- communicating (conferences, journals, blogs, twitter, social media platforms)

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- OpenNeuro, CONP, brainlife, OSF
- to report analyzes jupyter notebooks are used
- serve the community that enables them to share (e.g. BrainLife)
- Reports on grants. There are also other tools to help research institutions keep track of what researchers are doing.
- funders require now open access. Hard to provide the infrastructure needed. even harder to have recognition by the community -Vision: can we make a difference in the market place i.e., disrupt how journal work to create a platform that contains all information linking to all research outputs -access all research product as easily as possible
- there are companies making business that aim at organizing information for institutions
- tools to capture research activities for reporting are being developed
- modern venues that need to be considered; requires community to inform what venues they use or what's relevant for them
- services for this? there are many private companies which scrap the web